

Prathyoushada Prayoga – Concept of Antidote W.S.R. To Prayogasamucchaya (A Treatise on Ayurvedic Toxicology)

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ABSTRACT

There are many drugs including both plant and mineral origin, which cannot be utilized directly. Even though those drugs are having high therapeutic value, they can be utilized only after following proper Sodhana. Sodhana has a very important role to reduce the toxicity or Teekshanatha of those drugs. But if those drugs are taken accidentally or without following Sodhana, it will shows toxic reactions. Prathyoushadas are the drugs which used as antidote in such conditions. In Prayogasamucchaya, Prathyoushadas were explained in Ekadasha Paricchedam under the context of Asudha Bhakshana Chikitsa. Here author had explained Prathyoushada not only for Upavishas but also for some of the plant and mineral origin drugs if consumed without following Sodhana. Hence in this work an attempt is made to review the Prathyoushada explained in Prayogasamucchaya

KEYWORDS: Prayogasamucchaya, Visha, Sodhana, Prathyoushada

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INTRODUCTION

Prayogasamucchaya is one of the famous Malayalam repositories in *Visha Chikitsa*; which was written by *Kochunni Tampuran*, the foremost *Visha Vaidhya* in Kerala. He was the member of Kochi Royal family and he used to do *Visha Chikitsa* directly as well as with disciples. His treatment was so famous, as he treats poisoned people at any time without any discrimination. And even without payment. The entire textbook explains *Visha* and *Visha Chikitsa* in 11 Chapters and chapters are explained as *Paricchedam*. First 5 chapters are exclusively dedicated for *Sarpa* and *Damsa Chikitsa*, whereas 6th, 7th and 8th chapter explains *Mooshika*, *Vrischika*, *Lootha Chikitsa* respectively. 9th chapter includes the remaining all *Jangama Visha Chikitsa* such as *Nakula*, *Marjara*, *Manduka*, *Matsya*, *Alraka* etc and even *Manushya Visha Chikitsa*. And 10th chapter entirely explains *Dootha lakshana*. *Kai Visha*, *Sthavara Visha*, *Prathyoushada*,

Virudhahara and even *Agni* and *Mruqa Pareeksha* is explained in 11th chapter. And the textbook ends with *Samanya Vidhi*.

Prathyoushadas can be considered as antidotes which are used in management of Poisoning. This is different from *Prativisha*; as they are only *Visha dravyas* used in the management of another *Visha*. *Prathyoushadas* includes all *Dravyas*, even *Visha Dravyas*. In *Prayogasamucchaya* *Prathyoushadas* are explained in *Ekadasha Paricchedam* under the context of *Asudha Bhakshana Chikitsa*.^[1] Here the author had explained *Prathyoushadas* in context where someone consumes certain substances internally, for which *Sodhana* is required without following *Sodhana*. *Prathyoushada* for *Mahavisha*, *Upavishas*, *Dhatu Vishas*, other sort of *Sthavara Vishas* and *Madhya* are included. In this article an attempt is made to review on the *Prathyoushada* explained in this section.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Table no.1, Mahavisha with Prathyoushadas

Sl. No.	Mahavisha	Prathyoushadas
1.	Vatsanabha ^[2] (<i>Aconitum ferox</i> Wall. ex Ser.)	Triphala (<i>Amalaki</i> (<i>Phyllanthus emblica</i> L.), <i>Bibhitaki</i> (<i>Terminalia bellirica</i> (Gaertn.) Roxb.), and <i>Haritaki</i> (<i>Terminalia chebula</i> Retz.)) <i>Kashaya - Pana</i> <i>Neeli Moola</i> (<i>Indigofera tinctoria</i> L.) Water boiled with <i>Maricha</i> (<i>Piper nigrum</i> L.)- <i>Pana</i> <i>Triphala</i> (<i>Amalaki</i> (<i>Phyllanthus emblica</i> L.), <i>Bibhitaki</i> (<i>Terminalia bellirica</i> (Gaertn.) Roxb.), and <i>Haritaki</i> (<i>Terminalia chebula</i> Retz.)) <i>Kashaya, Ghrita, Ksheera- Pana</i> This is also good for <i>Pashana Visha</i>

Table no.2, Upavishas with Prathyoushadas

Sl. No.	Upavishas	Prathyoushadas
1.	<i>Kupilu</i> ^[3] (<i>Strychnos nux-vomica</i> L.)	<i>Gunja Pallava</i> (<i>Abrus precatorius</i> L.) should be made in to <i>Kalka</i> , it can be used as <i>Pana and Lepa</i> - this will reduce spasm and numbness fastly. <i>Ghrita, Madhu and Sita – Pana</i>
2.	<i>Kupilu Beeja</i> ^[4] (<i>Strychnos nuxvomica</i>)	<i>Jambu</i> (<i>Syzygium cumini</i> L.) <i>Patra Swarasa- Pana</i>
3.	<i>Arka Ksheera</i> ^[2] (<i>Calotropis procera</i>)	<i>Tila</i> (<i>Sesamum indicum</i> L.) <i>Kashaya with Guda- Pana</i>
4.	<i>Snuhi Ksheera</i> ^[2] (<i>Euphorbia nerifolia</i>)	<i>Avarthaki Beeja</i> (<i>Senna auriculata</i> (L.) Roxb.) and <i>Tila</i> (<i>Sesamum indicum</i> L.) <i>Kashaya with Sita- Pana</i>
5.	<i>Dattura Phala</i> ^[4] (<i>Datura metel</i> L.)	<i>Padmanala</i> (<i>Nelumbo nucifera</i> Gaertn.) (stalk of lotus) <i>Swarasa- Pana</i> <i>Padmanala</i> (<i>Nelumbo nucifera</i> Gaertn.) (stalk of lotus) <i>Kashaya- Pana</i>
6.	<i>Bhang</i> ^[5] (<i>Cannabis sativa</i> L.)	<i>Bimbi</i> (<i>Coccoloba indica</i> W.) (used to reduce the potency of <i>Bhang</i>) Warm <i>Ksheera</i> (milk) can be taken continuously Continuous <i>Shirodhara</i> with <i>Ksheera</i> (milk) <i>Nalikera Jala</i> (tender) (<i>Cocos nucifera</i> L.) can be given

Table no.3, Dhatuvishas with Prathyoushadas

Rasa		
Sl. No.	Rasa	Prathyoushadas
1.	<i>Parada</i> ^[6] (Mercury- Hg)	<i>Kushmanda Swarasa</i> (<i>Benincasa hispida</i> (Thunb.) Cogn.) / <i>Jambeera Swarasa</i> (<i>Citrus limon</i> (Linn.) Burm.) with <i>Sita- Pana</i> (should be taken Immediately) <i>Sodhita Gandhaka</i> (Sulphur) can also be given- <i>Gandhaka</i> in the weight of 2 <i>Masha</i> (<i>Vigna mungo</i> (L.) Hepper) should be taken and folded in <i>Nagavalli Patra</i> (<i>Piper betel</i> L.) –can be chewed <i>Krishna Tulasi</i> (<i>Ocimum tenuiflorum</i> L.), <i>Kushmanda</i> (<i>Benincasa hispida</i> (Thunb.) Cogn.), <i>Satapushpa</i> (<i>Anethum graveolans</i> L.), <i>Nagakesara</i> (<i>Mesua ferrea</i> Linn.), <i>Draksha</i> (<i>Vitis vinifera</i> L.), <i>Lavanga</i> (<i>Syzygium aromaticum</i> (L.) Merr.) – should be taken in equal quantity and made in to powder, add <i>Gandhaka</i> (Sulphur) to it and mix this powder in <i>Ksheera</i> and keep under sunlight –internal administration(each of the above said drugs can be taken individually following the same procedure) <i>Nagavalli Swarasa</i> (<i>Piper betel</i> L.), <i>Bringaraja Swarasa</i> (<i>Eclipta alba</i> (L.) Hassk.), <i>Tulasi Swarasa</i> (<i>Ocimum sanctum</i> L.), <i>Aja Ksheera</i> - should be taken in equal quantity, apply on entire body and massage properly. Continue the same for 3 days and 4 th day <i>Snana</i> can be done with boiled and cooled water (this will help to reduce burning sensation etc.)

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Maharaas		
2.	<i>Abraka</i> ^[7] (Mica)	<i>Amalaki</i> (without seeds) (<i>Amalaki</i> (<i>Phyllanthus emblica</i> L.) should grind in water and can be consumed for 3 days Consuming <i>Ksheera</i> (milk) with <i>Sita</i> frequently can also be practiced
3.	<i>Makshika</i> ^[8] (Chalcopyrite- Cu ₂ S Fe ₂ S ₃)	<i>Kulatha Kashaya</i> (<i>Macrotyloma uniflorum</i> (Lam.) Verdc.)- <i>Pana</i> <i>Dadima Kashaya</i> (<i>Punica granatum</i> Linn.)- <i>Pana</i>
4.	<i>Shilajathu</i> ^[9] (Asphaltum Punjabium)	Consume <i>Ghrita</i> mixed with <i>Maricha</i> (<i>Piper nigrum</i> L.) for 7 days
5.	<i>Tutta</i> ^[7] (Copper sulphate-CuSO ₄ 5H ₂ O)	<i>Jambeera Swarasa</i> (<i>Citrus limon</i> (Linn.) can be consumed in early morning <i>Laja choorna</i> (Popped rice) can be consumed by mixing with boiled and cooled water
Uparasas		
6.	<i>Gandhaka</i> ^[3] (Sulphur - S)	<i>Takra</i> (buttermilk) mixed with <i>Chandana</i> (<i>Santalum album</i> L.) - <i>Pana</i> <i>Amalaki Swarasa</i> (<i>Phyllanthus emblica</i> L.) mixed with <i>Usheera</i> (<i>Vetiveria zizanioides</i> (L.) Nash) - <i>Pana</i>
7.	<i>Kasisa</i> ^[8] (Ferrous sulphate- FeSO ₄ 7H ₂ O)	<i>Jambeera Swarasa</i> (<i>Citrus limon</i> (Linn.) - <i>Pana</i>
8.	<i>Haratala</i> ^[10] (Orpiment- As ₂ S ₃)	Consume <i>Swarasa</i> of ripened <i>Dadima</i> (<i>Punica granatum</i> Linn.) for many times One can also consume <i>Jiraka Choorna</i> (<i>Cuminum cyminum</i> L.) with <i>Sita</i>
9.	<i>Thalaga</i> ^[9] (Orpiment-As ₂ S ₃)	<i>Kashaya</i> prepared out of <i>Madhuka</i> (<i>Madhuca longifolia</i> (Koenig)), <i>Nikunchika</i> (<i>Acacia caisia</i> (L.) Willd.) and <i>Triphala</i> (<i>Amalaki</i> (<i>Phyllanthus emblica</i> L.), <i>Bibhitaki</i> (<i>Terminalia bellirica</i> (Gaertn.) Roxb.), and <i>Haritaki</i> (<i>Terminalia chebula</i> Retz.)) in equal quantity should consume in morning
10.	<i>Manashila</i> ^[9] (Realgar- As ₂ S ₂)	<i>Triphala</i> (<i>Amalaki</i> (<i>Phyllanthus emblica</i> L.), <i>Bibhitaki</i> (<i>Terminalia bellirica</i> (Gaertn.) Roxb.), and <i>Haritaki</i> (<i>Terminalia chebula</i> Retz.)) without seeds should grind in the female <i>Aja mutra</i> (goat,s urine)- <i>Pana</i>
Sadharana Rasa		
11.	<i>Hingula</i> ^[9] (Cinnabar-HgS)	Consume <i>Patola Swarasa</i> (<i>Trichosanthes dioica</i> Roxb.), <i>Ardraka Swarsaa</i> (<i>Zingiber officinale</i> Roscoe) and <i>Nari Ksheera</i> (breast milk) in equal quantity Consume <i>Nirgundi Patra Swarasa</i> (<i>Vitex negundo</i> L.)and <i>Nari Ksheera</i> (breast milk) in equal quantity
12.	<i>Pashana</i> ^[5]	Equal quantity of <i>Karavellaka Patra Swarasa</i> (<i>Momordica charantia</i> L.) and <i>Nari Ksheera</i> (breast milk) can be taken
Dhatu		
13.	<i>Swarna</i> ^[13] (Gold- Au)	<i>Haritaki Choorna</i> (<i>Haritaki</i> (<i>Terminalia chebula</i> Retz.)) with <i>Sita</i> for 3 days
14.	<i>Rajata</i> ^[12] (Silver-Ag)	<i>Sita</i> and <i>Madhu</i> in equal quantity can be consumed for 3 days
15.	<i>Tamra</i> ^[11] (Copper- Cu)	Water boiled and cooled with the Rice or <i>Moola</i> of <i>Nivara</i> (<i>Hygroryza aristata</i> (Retz.) Nees ex Wight & Arn.) can be consumed by adding <i>Sita</i> in early morning for 3 days
16.	<i>Loha</i> ^[10] (Iron- Fe) & <i>Ayaskantha</i> ^[10] (Magnet)	<i>Ela beeja</i> (<i>Elettaria cardomomam</i> (L.) Maton)should be powdered and consumed with <i>Ganda Sarkara</i> and <i>Madhu</i> for 3 days Same can be taken as <i>Pana</i>
17.	<i>Saraloha</i> ^[10] (Steel)	Add <i>Trivrut</i> (<i>Operculina turpethum</i> (L.) Silva Manso) and <i>Saindhava Choorna</i> (Rock salt) in hot water- <i>Pana</i>
18.	<i>Purana Kittam</i> ^[10] (Ferric oxide- Fe ₂ O ₃)	Consume <i>Haritaki Choorna</i> (<i>Haritaki</i> (<i>Terminalia chebula</i> Retz.)) with <i>madhu</i> for 3 days

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Putilauha		
19.	<i>Vanga</i> ^[12] (Tin-Sn)	<i>Keetamari Moola Kalka</i> (<i>Aristolochia bracteolata</i> Lam.) can be consumed in warm water in early morning for 3 days
20.	<i>Tutthanaga</i> ^[12] (Yasada- Zn)	<i>Triphala Choorna</i> (<i>Amalaki</i> (<i>Phyllanthus emblica</i> L.), <i>Bibhitaki</i> (<i>Terminalia bellirica</i> (Gaertn.) Roxb.), and <i>Haritaki</i> (<i>Terminalia chebula</i> Retz.)) can be consumed in early morning for 3 days
21.	<i>Naga</i> ^[10] (Lead- Pb)	<i>Vacha</i> (white variety) (<i>Acorus calamus</i> Linn.) made in to <i>Choorna</i> with <i>Haritaki</i> (<i>Haritaki</i> (<i>Terminalia chebula</i> Retz.)) and mix equal quantity <i>Sita</i> and consume for 3 days
Misralauha		
22.	<i>Kamsya</i> ^[12] (Bronze)	Ripened <i>Chincha</i> (<i>Tamarindus indica</i> L.) should consume in boiled and cooled water
23.	<i>Pittala</i> ^[12] (Brass)	<i>Tandulodaka</i> (Rice water)- <i>Pana</i>
Ratna		
24.	<i>Pravala</i> ^[8] (Coral- CaCO ₃)	<i>Ksheera</i> (milk) with <i>Sita</i> and <i>Madhu</i> can be consumed
25.	<i>Navaratana</i> ^[7]	<i>Ghrita</i> , <i>Madhu</i> , <i>Sita</i> , <i>Ksheera</i> (milk) can be consumed(same can be given for <i>Mouktika</i> (Pearl))
26.	<i>Uparatna</i> ^[7]	Same as <i>Navartana</i>
Sudha Varga		
27.	<i>Sudha</i> ^[5] (Lime- CaCO ₃)	Equal quantity of <i>Eranda Taila</i> (<i>Ricinus communis</i> L.), and <i>Nari Ksheera</i> (breast milk) can be used

Table no.4, Miscellaneous Drugs with Prathyoushadas

Sl. No.	Drugs	Prathyoushadas
1.	<i>Chirabilwa</i> ^[3] (<i>Holoptelea integrifolia</i> (Roxb.) Planch.)	<i>Eranda Beeja</i> (<i>Ricinus communis</i> L.), <i>Nava Gritha</i> , <i>Satavari</i> (<i>Asparagus racemosus</i> Willd.) can be consumed
2.	<i>Citraka</i> ^[3] (<i>Plumbago zeylanica</i> L.)	<i>Eranda Beeja</i> (<i>Ricinus communis</i> L.), <i>Nava Gritha</i> , <i>Satavari</i> (<i>Asparagus racemosus</i> Willd.) can be consumed
3.	<i>Dravanti</i> ^[2] (<i>Jatropha curcas</i> Linn.)	<i>Ksheera</i> prepared out with <i>Yastimadhu</i> (<i>Glycyrrhiza glabra</i> L.), <i>Draksha</i> (<i>Vitis vinifera</i> L.), <i>Kharjura</i> (<i>Phoenix dactylifera</i> L.) can be taken with <i>Sita</i> , <i>Ghrita</i> , <i>Madhu</i>
4.	<i>Jyotismati</i> ^[14] (<i>Celastrus paniculatus</i> Willd.)	<i>Kashaya</i> prepared out of <i>Padmanala</i> (<i>Nelumbo nucifera</i> Gaertn.) (stalk of lotus) can be consumed with <i>Ghrita</i> and <i>Guda</i> <i>Kashaya</i> made out of <i>Gunja Moola</i> (<i>Abrus precatorius</i> L.) (<i>asodhitha</i>) <i>Kalka - Pana</i> <i>Kashaya</i> prepared out of <i>Musta</i> (<i>Cyperus rotundus</i> L.)
5.	<i>Kumari</i> ^[4] (<i>Aloe barbadensis</i> Mill.)	<i>Snuhi bhasma</i> (<i>Euphorbia nerifolia</i> L.) with <i>Saindhava</i> (Rock salt) can be taken with lukewarm water
6.	<i>Citraka</i> ^[4] (<i>Plumbago zeylanica</i> L.)	<i>Tila</i> (<i>Sesamum indicum</i> L.) should be consumed with <i>Nava guda</i>
7.	<i>Gandhira</i> ^[4] (<i>Cayratia carnos</i> (Wall. ex Wight) Gagnep.)	<i>Chincha</i> (<i>Tamarindus indica</i> L.) <i>Patra Swarasa - Pana</i>
8.	<i>Kakanasa Phala</i> ^[4] (<i>Trichosanthes Tricuspidata</i> Lour.)	<i>Takra Pana</i> (buttermilk) <i>Kashaya</i> prepared out of <i>Chandana</i> (<i>Santalum album</i> L.) with <i>Guda</i> can be taken immediately
9.	<i>Jatiphala</i> ^[15] (<i>Myristica fragrans</i> Houtt.)	<i>Kashaya</i> prepared out of <i>Kola</i> (<i>Zizyphus jujuba</i>) , <i>Kharjura</i> (<i>Phoenix dactylifera</i> L.) and <i>Draksha</i> (<i>Vitis vinifera</i> L.) can be taken with <i>Sita</i>

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10.	<i>Avarthaki Beeja</i> ^[5] (<i>Cassia auriculata</i> Linn.)	<i>Triphala Kashaya</i> (<i>Amalaki</i> (<i>Phyllanthus emblica</i> L.), <i>Bibhitaki</i> (<i>Terminalia bellirica</i> (Gaertn.) Roxb.), and <i>Haritaki</i> (<i>Terminalia chebula</i> Retz.)) – <i>Pana</i>
11.	<i>Tuvaraka Beeja</i> ^[5] (<i>Hydnocarpus laurifolia</i> (Dennst.) Sleumer)	<i>Kashaya</i> prepared out of <i>Triphala</i> (<i>Amalaki</i> (<i>Phyllanthus emblica</i> L.), <i>Bibhitaki</i> (<i>Terminalia bellirica</i> (Gaertn.) Roxb.), and <i>Haritaki</i> (<i>Terminalia chebula</i> Retz.)) and <i>Patola</i> (<i>Trichosanthes dioica</i> Roxb.)
12.	<i>Karpura</i> ^[9] (<i>Cinnamomum camphora</i> (L.) J. Presl.) (if consumed in excess quantity)	Water boiled and cooled with <i>Dhanyaka kalka</i> (<i>Coriandrum sativum</i> Linn.) should be consumed by adding <i>Sita</i> <i>Swarasa</i> of <i>Mahisha Sakrut</i> (female buffalo faeces) with <i>Sita</i> can be consumed
13.	<i>Madhya</i> ^[5] (Alcohol)	<i>Jambeera Swarasa</i> (<i>Citrus limon</i> (Linn.) <i>Madhya</i> (Alcohol) can also be consumed <i>Madhya</i> (Alcohol) with <i>Jambeera Swarasa</i> (<i>Citrus limon</i> (Linn.) can be taken immediately

Table no.5. Common Prathyoushadas for all drugs

Sl. No.		Prathyoushadas
1.	Can be used in all <i>Visha</i> explained above ^[8]	<i>Kashaya</i> prepared out of <i>Akathi</i> stem bark (<i>Sesbania grandiflora</i> (L.) Poiret), <i>Triphala</i> (<i>Amalaki</i> (<i>Phyllanthus emblica</i> L.), <i>Bibhitaki</i> (<i>Terminalia bellirica</i> (Gaertn.) Roxb.), and <i>Haritaki</i> (<i>Terminalia chebula</i> Retz.)) taken in equal can be consumed
2.	Can be used in all <i>Visha</i> explained above ^[16]	<i>Bilwa moola</i> (<i>Aegle marmelos</i> (L.) Correa), <i>Chandana</i> (<i>Santalum album</i> L.), <i>Sunti</i> (<i>Zingiber officinale</i> Roscoe), <i>Ushira</i> (<i>Vetiveria zizanioides</i> (L.) Nash), <i>Hribera</i> (<i>Pavonia odorata</i>), <i>Triphala</i> (<i>Amalaki</i> (<i>Phyllanthus emblica</i> L.), <i>Bibhitaki</i> (<i>Terminalia bellirica</i> (Gaertn.) Roxb.), <i>Devadaru</i> (<i>Cedrus deodara</i> (Roxb.) G. Don), <i>Neeli</i> (<i>Indigofera tinctoria</i> L.), <i>Tanduliya</i> (<i>Amaranthus spinosus</i>), <i>Arkaraga</i> (<i>Lodoicea maldivica</i> (Poir.) Pers.), <i>Sariva</i> (<i>Hemidesmus indicus</i> (L.) R.Br.), <i>Nimba twak</i> (<i>Azardirachta indica</i> A. Juss.), <i>Aindri Moola</i> (<i>Citrullus colocynthis</i> (Linn.) Schrader), <i>Durva</i> (<i>Cynodon dactylon</i> (L.) Pers.), <i>Pushkaramoola</i> (<i>Inula racemosa</i> Hook. f.), <i>Nagadanti Moola</i> (<i>Baliospermum montanum</i>), <i>Agasthya twak</i> (<i>Sesbania grandiflora</i> (L.) Poiret) these all should be taken in equal quantity and <i>Kashaya</i> should prepare and can be consumed with <i>Sita</i> , <i>ghrita</i> and <i>Jiraka</i> (<i>Cuminum cyminum</i> L.)

DISCUSSION

Prathyoushada by the term, it means the *Oushada* which is administered as counter drug. It can be considered as antidote, but *Prathyoushada* are not *Prativisha* as they are the *Visha Dravyas* which utilized in the management of another *Visha*. *Prathyoushada* includes both *Visha* and *Nirvisha Dravyas*. As we go through the above data, it is clear that *Prathyoushadas* for about 47 *Dravyas* have been explained and about 50 drugs are utilized in the management of those *Vishas* as single drug or formulations. That includes *Prathyoushadas* for *Mahavisha*, *Upavishas*, *Dhatu Vishas* and other *Visha Dravyas*. Even at the end, common *Prathyoushada* is also explained so as it can be utilized in all condition even if the specific antidotes are not available. And in majority conditions either single drug or very minimum drugs were utilized. The main treatment modality explained is *Pana* with more *Kashaya* and *Swarasa* preparation. Hence showing that they have chosen the easiest method of preparation and mode of administration as it is an emergency condition. The most repeated *Dravya* used in the management is *Triphala*, showing its importance in *Visha Chikitsa*. *Upavishas* such as *Gunja*, *Eranda*, *Snuhi* are also included in the management of some of the *Vishas* as *Prativisha*. *Sita*, *Madhu*, *Ghritha*, *Ksheera* are repeatedly used *Anupanas*.

As going through the above list it is clear that, not all *Dravyas* are having *Visha Guna* and even some of the above mentioned drugs are used without following *Sodhana*. But here author have mentioned that these are the drugs that should be taken after *Sodhana*, if at all consumed without following *Sodhana* then these *Prathyoushada* should be consumed. So it can be considered that author have included those drugs which *Teekshna* in nature and requires more care while incorporating in therapeutic use. For example; *Citraka* and *Chirabilwa*, both are included under *Bhedaniya Mahakashaya Varga*^[17] in *Charaka Samhitha* and these drugs are capable of causing *Bhedana* action, as the *Prakruthi*, *Koshta*, *Agni* etc. varies from individual to individual it may cause harmful effects in some individuals, whereas no harmful effects in others, so as to avoid such situations *Sodhana* was suggested and even *Prathyoushadas* were mentioned to manage those condition. Even after explaining *Prathyoushadas* author himself mentioned that “even these drugs are having *Dosha* if purified, it will be equal to *Amruth*. If administered without following *Sodhana*, above procedures can be followed and even if some of the drugs are *Nirdosha*, may become *Dushta* due to combination with other drugs”.^[18] This may be the rationality of explaining *Prathyoushadas* in detail for many drugs.

CONCLUSION

Ayurveda always gives importance to the safety of the patient. In order to assure that various methods are followed, one among that is following *Sodhana* for toxic and such drugs before utilizing. As *Agadatantra* being the branch that dealing with *Visha* and *Chikitsa*, various treatment procedures and exclusives *Yogas* are explained for the management of *Visha*. *Prayogasamucchaya* one of the famous Malayalam *Visha Chikitsa* textbook has explained *Oushada* in the management of drugs if taken without following *Sodhana*. Chapter includes about 47 drugs without *Prathyoushadas*. Knowledge on such topic will help the physician to manage various emergency conditions and can even take precautions.

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